

Multiport Y-Converter for Three-Phase AC Grid Integration with DC Systems

Ahmed Y. Farag, Davide Biadene, Tommaso Caldognetto, Paolo Mattavelli
Dept. of Management and Engineering (DTG), University of Padova, Vicenza, Italy
Email: ahmedyahiafarag.abdelfattah@phd.unipd.it, davide.biadene@unipd.it,
tommaso.caldognetto@unipd.it, paolo.mattavelli@unipd.it

Abstract—The challenges associated with the escalating demand for electrical energy and environmental concerns tied to traditional energy sources underscore the need for greater penetration of renewable energy sources. To ensure stable and reliable energy production, energy storage systems and an interface with the AC grid can compensate for the intermittent nature of renewable sources. Hence, multiport converters are proposed to consolidate various energy ports into a single hub, enhancing system efficiency and power density. This paper proposes a single-stage non-isolated multiport converter to interface the three-phase AC grid with DC systems. The proposed converter features buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports, enabling it to directly interface with a wide range of DC systems. Additionally, the absence of bulky intermediate DC-link capacitors and transformers in the proposed topology contributes to improved power density and reduced costs. The paper presents the converter's operation and analysis, along with an evaluation of semiconductor stresses and losses. Finally, simulation and experimental results are presented to highlight the converter's performance under different operating conditions.

Index Terms—AC-DC power conversion, Multiport converters, Three-phase inverters, Three-phase rectifiers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Meeting the escalating demand for electrical energy poses challenges, with traditional sources contributing to environmental issues. While renewable energy sources (RESs) offer a solution by allowing carbon-free generation, their intermittent energy production due to fluctuating weather remains a primary obstacle. To address this, distributed energy storage systems are integrated, smoothing power flows and ensuring a stable power supply [1], [2]. Integration is possible using conventional power topologies with cascaded multi-stage connections [3], but the scenario also opens opportunities for optimized architectures with potentially enhanced performance [4].

Multiport power converters (MPCs) offer a solution for consolidating multiple energy ports into a single hub [5]. As a result, MPCs could provide valuable solutions to distribution networks by facilitating increased utilization of RESs, energy storage systems, and loads with diverse electrical properties. Achieving these functions with MPCs requires fewer conversion stages than using multiple DC-DC and AC-DC converters in cascaded connections, potentially resulting in higher efficiency and power density with a lower cost [6].

Several studies have addressed enabling MPCs in residential and distribution networks [7]. DC MPCs have been proposed

to directly interface RESs and energy storage through various configurations, including isolated multi-active bridge converters, semi-isolated converters, and non-isolated converters [8]. Although these converters can interface with the AC grid through an inverter stage, the cascaded connection between the DC MPCs and the inverter stage compromises the effectiveness of this solution.

To overcome this limitation, AC-DC MPCs have been proposed to interface single-phase and three-phase AC grids with DC systems [9]. Although AC-DC MPCs have the advantage of providing a direct interface with AC grids and DC systems without the need for additional power stages, the proposed converters suffer from limitations. Firstly, most of the proposed topologies rely on transformer isolation for establishing the MPC, which in turn degrades converter performance in terms of power density and cost. Therefore, unless galvanic isolation is mandatory, such as when a high voltage gain is required, non-isolated AC-DC MPCs can offer an effective solution in terms of size and cost. Secondly, constraints on the operating range of the proposed converters, either the lack of capability to provide buck-boost operation or bidirectional power flow at DC ports, result in losing the advantage of directly interfacing different DC systems [10], [11].

In this paper, a single-stage non-isolated MPC is proposed to interface the three-phase AC grid with DC systems. The proposed converter features a buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow at all ports and hence the converter can directly interface a wide range of DC systems. Additionally, the converter offers single-stage power conversion among the different ports, eliminating the need for an intermediate DC-link capacitor. Combining the benefits of having a single-stage power conversion and eliminating the bulky components as the intermediate DC-link capacitors and the isolating transformers can potentially lead to an improved efficiency and power density.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Sec. II explains the converter operation and analysis, Sec. III presents an evaluation of semiconductor devices stresses and losses for a wide voltage range of DC ports, ranging from 350 V to 800 V. Simulation and experimental results are discussed in Sec. IV and Sec. V, respectively. Finally, Sec. VI reports the conclusion.

Fig. 1: A schematic of the proposed multiport Y-converter.

II. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION AND ANALYSIS

Fig. 1 displays the proposed converter. The topology builds upon the Y-converter, as introduced in [12], [13], transforming it from a two-port configuration into a multi-port one capable of connecting multiple DC ports to the three-phase AC grid. In its original form, the two-port Y-converter comprised three four-switch buck-boost modules. However, the proposed converter modifies each module by expanding it into a six-switch DC-DC converter. In the context of a three-port converter, the upgraded design includes a shared buck half-bridge and two boost half-bridges, establishing connections to the DC ports. To accommodate additional DC ports, the configuration can be easily expanded by incorporating one boost converter into each module for every extra DC port.

Similar to the two-port Y-converter, the three modified modules are interconnected at a central point denoted as m , which functions as the neutral point for the Y-connection of the modules. As each module serves as a DC-DC converter, it is crucial to maintain a non-negative voltage on the AC side of the module ($v_{\{a,b,c\}m} \geq 0V$). To achieve this, an offset voltage is necessary between grid neutral point n and m . A constant offset voltage (V_{off}) is then applied, which must be higher than the peak value of the AC grid phase voltage (\hat{V}_m). The AC-side voltages v_{am} , v_{bm} , and v_{cm} can be mathematically expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{am}(t) &= \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{off} \\ v_{bm}(t) &= \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t - 2\pi/3) + V_{off} \\ v_{cm}(t) &= \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + 2\pi/3) + V_{off} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where ω is the AC grid frequency in rad/s.

The analysis of the converter is presented by considering a single module (module a), as depicted in Fig. 2, and it similarly applies to the other modules too. This module consists of the two inductors L_1 and L_2 along with three half-bridges: one on the AC side, labeled as *Buck a*, and the others on the DC sides, labeled as *Boost a1* and *Boost a2*. In the subsequent analysis, it is assumed that at least one of the DC ports' voltage is lower than the peak of the AC side voltage ($\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$), and V_{dc1} is

Fig. 2: Module a of the proposed converter.

lower than V_{dc2} . Based on these assumptions, the *Buck a* and *Boost a1* half-bridges are under control, ensuring that only one of them is modulated at any given moment, while the other remains clamped based on the values of v_{am} and V_{dc1} , whereas *Boost a2* will be modulated continuously.

When v_{am} is greater than V_{dc1} , that is, when $t_1 < t < t_2$, as illustrated in Fig. 3, the *Buck a* half-bridge keeps switching, while the *Boost a1* half-bridge is clamped with S_{a3} on and S_{a4} off. To determine the duty cycle of S_{a1} , denoted as $d_{buck,a}$, the following calculation can be applied:

$$d_{buck,a}(t) = \frac{V_{dc1}}{v_{am}(t)} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{off}} \quad (2)$$

and the duty cycle of S_{a2} is the complementary of $d_{buck,a}$.

For the *Boost a2* half-bridge, it operates with a fixed duty cycle during this period, depending on the ratio between V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} . The duty cycle of S_{a5} , denoted as $d_{boost,a2}$, can be calculated as follows:

$$d_{boost,a2} = \frac{V_{dc1}}{V_{dc2}} \quad (3)$$

and the duty cycle of S_{a6} is the complementary of $d_{boost,a2}$.

The AC grid current of phase a , denoted as i_a , is assumed to be pure sinusoidal and in phase with its corresponding phase voltage v_a and then can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i_a(t) &= \hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t) = (\hat{I}_{m1} + \hat{I}_{m2}) \sin(\omega t) \\ &= \left(\frac{2P_{dc1}}{3\hat{V}_m} + \frac{2P_{dc2}}{3\hat{V}_m} \right) \sin(\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} represent the power delivered to DC ports 1 and 2, respectively, and \hat{I}_m denotes the peak phase current.

The summation of average inductor currents ($i_{La1,av} + i_{La2,av}$) can be derived by applying Kirchhoff's Current Law (KCL) at the AC input of the module, as follows:

$$i_{La1,av}(t) + i_{La2,av}(t) = \frac{i_a(t) - i_{Cf,a}(t)}{d_{buck,a}(t)} \quad (5)$$

where $i_{Cf,a}$ represents the current through the input capacitor C_f . By neglecting $i_{Cf,a}$, the equation can be simplified as

Fig. 3: Key waveforms of module a of the proposed converter.

follows:

$$i_{La1,av}(t) + i_{La2,av}(t) = \frac{i_a(t)}{d_{buck,a}(t)} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)}{d_{buck,a}(t)} \quad (6)$$

Using (4) and (6), $i_{La1,av}$ and $i_{La2,av}$ can be determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{La1,av}(t) &= \frac{\hat{I}_{m1} \sin(\omega t)}{d_{buck,a}(t)} \\ i_{La2,av}(t) &= \frac{\hat{I}_{m2} \sin(\omega t)}{d_{buck,a}(t)} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Similarly, when v_{am} is lower than V_{dc1} , that is, when $0 \leq t \leq t_1$ and $t_2 \leq t \leq T$ as illustrated in Fig. 3, the *Boost, a1* half-bridge keeps switching, while the *Buck, a* half-bridge is clamped with S_{a1} on and S_{a2} off. To determine the duty cycle of S_{a3} , denoted as $d_{boost,a1}$, the following calculation can be applied:

$$d_{boost,a1}(t) = \frac{v_{am}(t)}{V_{dc1}} = \frac{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{off}}{V_{dc1}} \quad (8)$$

TABLE I: Parameters of the proposed converter

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rated AC power	$P_{ac,r}$	10 kW
Rated DC power	$P_{dc1,r}, P_{dc2,r}$	5 kW
AC line voltage, frequency	V_{ll}, f_o	400 V, 50 Hz
DC voltage	V_{dc1}, V_{dc2}	350–800 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	62.5 kHz
Inductance	L_1, L_2	330 μ H

and the duty cycle of S_{a4} is the complementary of $d_{boost,a}$. For the *Boost a2* half-bridge, $d_{boost,a2}$, can be calculated as follows:

$$d_{boost,a2}(t) = \frac{v_{am}(t)}{V_{dc2}} = \frac{\hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t) + V_{off}}{V_{dc2}} \quad (9)$$

Using (7) and given that $d_{buck,a}$ equal to 1 in this mode, $i_{La1,av}$ and $i_{La2,av}$ can be determined as:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{La1,av}(t) &= \hat{I}_{m1} \sin(\omega t) \\ i_{La2,av}(t) &= \hat{I}_{m2} \sin(\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

III. SEMICONDUCTOR DEVICES STRESSES AND LOSSES

The voltage and current stresses of the semiconductor devices of the proposed converter are analyzed in this section. This analysis aids in appropriately sizing and selecting the semiconductor devices. The converter's specifications and ratings are outlined in Table I, assuming the converter's connection to the European low-voltage grid via its AC port and interfacing with two DC ports ranging from 350 V to 800 V. The AC and DC power ratings are selected for residential and commercial applications and are chosen to be 10 kW and 5 kW, respectively.

In addition to the stresses on semiconductor devices, the conduction and switching losses of the devices are presented at rated power for different voltage levels of the DC ports.

A. Semiconductor devices stresses

1) *Voltage stresses*: the AC-side buck half-bridges *Buck, (a, b, c)* process the AC-side voltages $v_{(a,b,c)m}$, respectively. Therefore, the related switches are subjected to a time-varying voltage of maximum value that equals $\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$. Meanwhile, the DC-side boost half-bridges *Boost, (a, b, c)1* and *Boost, (a, b, c)2* present voltage stress equal to their respective DC port voltage.

2) *Current stresses*: the RMS current stresses of the semiconductor devices at rated power are displayed in Fig. 4 using fitted contour plots. As stated in the previous section, the presented analysis assumes that at least one of the DC ports' voltage is lower than $\hat{V}_m + V_{off}$. In the presented current stresses plot, one of the DC ports is always limited to 600 V, while the other can reach the specified rated DC voltage (i.e., 800 V).

Considering the current stresses of the *Buck, (a, b, c)* switches ($S_{(a,b,c)1}$, $S_{(a,b,c)2}$), the current stresses increase as the DC ports' voltage decreases due to higher values of i_{La1}

Fig. 4: Fitted contour plots illustrating the RMS current stresses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.

and i_{La2} in buck mode. Conversely, as the DC ports' voltage increases, the current stresses decrease, especially for $S_{(a,b,c)2}$, where the current stresses at the high voltage limits of the DC ports are four times lower than the current stresses at the low voltage limits.

For the current stresses of the $Boost(a,b,c)1$ and $Boost(a,b,c)2$ switches, as in a typical DC-DC boost converter, the current stresses of the upper switches ($S_{(a,b,c)3}$, $S_{(a,b,c)5}$) increase as their corresponding DC port voltage decreases, while the current stresses of the lower switches ($S_{(a,b,c)4}$, $S_{(a,b,c)6}$) increase as their corresponding DC port voltage increases.

B. Semiconductor devices losses

The semiconductor losses of the proposed converter are evaluated through simulations, considering 1.2 kV SiC MOSFETs. For $S_{(a,b,c)1}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)2}$, a SiC MOSFET with nominal on-state resistance of 30 m Ω (IMZ120R030M1H) is selected, while for the other devices, a 60 m Ω SiC MOSFET (IMZ120R060M1H) is chosen.

The fitted contour plots of conduction losses, switching losses, and total semiconductor losses are presented in Fig. 5. Conduction losses are maximum at low DC port voltages, primarily due to their significant dependence on the higher current stress of devices $S_{(a,b,c)1}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)2}$. Consequently, the trend of the conduction losses contour plot closely mirrors the contour plot of the current stresses of $S_{(a,b,c)1}$ and $S_{(a,b,c)2}$.

The switching losses of the proposed converter are primarily influenced by two factors: the inductor current, equivalent to the switching current of the devices, which increases at low DC port voltages, and the DC ports' voltage, equivalent to the switching voltage of $Boost(a,b,c)1$ and $Boost(a,b,c)2$ devices. As a result, switching losses are maximum when one of the DC ports' voltage is minimized while the other is maximized.

Finally, the calculated total semiconductor losses for the selected devices range from 100 W to 180 W, constituting 1% to 1.8% of the converter's rated power.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Simulation results of the proposed converter are presented in Fig. 6 to showcase its performance under different operating conditions. The simulations consider rated AC grid voltage and V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 400 V and 500 V, respectively. Additionally, the power delivered to V_{dc1} (P_{dc1}) is fixed at 5 kW.

Three different operating conditions are presented in this section. In the first operating condition, demonstrated in Fig. 6a, P_{dc2} is set to 5 kW, indicating that both DC systems are absorbing power from the AC grid. As evident from the waveforms, these simulation results match the waveforms discussed in the analysis section, exhibiting pure sinusoidal AC grid currents and positive AC module voltages, given that V_{off} is selected to equal 340 V.

Fig. 5: Fitted contour plots illustrating the power losses of the semiconductor devices in the proposed converter at rated power.

Fig. 6: Simulation results of the proposed converter under P_{dc1} equal to 5 kW and different values of P_{dc2} .

In Fig. 6b, P_{dc2} is set to 0 kW. In this case, power flows only from the AC grid to V_{dc1} , and the average current flowing in the L_2 inductors is controlled to zero, with only a high-frequency ripple current flowing through L_2 .

The third operating condition is displayed in Fig. 6c where P_{dc2} is set to -5 kW. In this case, both DC systems are directly exchanging active power through the proposed converter, and hence no active power is drawn from the AC grid. The AC grid currents are minimized, and only the current due to the reactive power drawn by C_f flows.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 7 depicts the experimental setup of the proposed converter, which serves the purpose of validating its operation and confirming the accuracy of the presented waveforms. The prototype consists of six Imperix SiC power modules (PEB8024 with C2M0080120D SiC MOSFETs) for the boost

half-bridges and three half-bridges with UF4SC120023K4S SiC MOSFETs featuring lower on-state resistance compared to the boost half-bridges devices due to higher current stresses. Control is achieved using two B-box controllers configured in a master-slave arrangement. The emulation of AC grid and DC systems is facilitated by bidirectional AC and DC power supplies. A single-stage input filter, with parameters $L_f = 1.2$ mH and $C_f = 10$ μ F, is utilized, while 330 μ H inductors are employed for L_1 and L_2 .

The experimental waveforms in Fig. 8 depict the operation of the converter with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} set to 360 V and 400 V, respectively, while the ac grid voltage remains at its rated value. Both P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} are set to 3 kW, indicating that both MGs are absorbing power from the AC grid. As evident from the waveforms, the AC currents demonstrate sinusoidal behavior and are well-synchronized with the AC voltages,

Fig. 7: Picture of the experimental prototype of the proposed converter.

Fig. 8: Experimental waveforms of the proposed converter with V_{dc1} and V_{dc2} are set to 360 V and 400 V and with P_{dc1} and P_{dc2} both equal to 3 kW.

resulting in a measured power factor of 0.99. The measured efficiency of the prototype at this operating point is 94.75%.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a single-stage non-isolated MPC designed to interlink the three-phase AC grid with DC systems. The primary motivations for this converter include its single-stage power conversion capability among different ports, which potentially leads to improved efficiency and power density. Furthermore, the absence of bulky intermediate DC-

link capacitors and transformers in the proposed topology contributes to enhanced power density and cost reduction. Additionally, the proposed MPC boasts buck-boost capability and bidirectional power flow across all ports, regardless of the DC ports' voltage, allowing for direct interfacing with a wide range of DC systems. The paper thoroughly discusses the operational and analytical aspects of the proposed converter, along with an assessment of semiconductor stresses and losses. Moreover, simulation and experimental results are provided to demonstrate the converter's performance under various operating conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme in the framework of the project "iPLUG" with grant agreement number 101069770.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Huang, D. Zhou, L. Wang, Z. Shen, and Y. Li, "A Review of Single-Stage Multiport Inverters for Multisource Applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 6566-6584, 2023.
- [2] A. Y. Farag, T. Younis, D. Biadene, and P. Mattavelli, "AC Grid-DC Microgrid Coupling with High-Performance Three-Phase Single-Stage Bidirectional Converters," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 17, article number 6106, 2023.
- [3] A. Y. Farag, D. Biadene, P. Mattavelli, and T. Younis, "Three-phase Four-wire Bidirectional Y-converter for an Enhanced Interface between the AC Grid and the Unipolar DC Microgrid," in *2023 8th IEEE Workshop on the Electronic Grid (eGRID)*, pp. 1-6, 2023.
- [4] A. K. Bhattacharjee, N. Kutkut, and I. Batarseh, "Review of Multiport Converters for Solar and Energy Storage Integration," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 1431-1445, Feb. 2019.
- [5] T. Pereira, F. Hoffmann, R. Zhu and M. Liserre, "A Comprehensive Assessment of Multiwinding Transformer-Based DC-DC Converters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 9, pp. 10020-10036, 2021.
- [6] L. Dorn-Gomba, P. Magne, B. Danen, and A. Emadi, "On the Concept of the Multi-Source Inverter for Hybrid Electric Vehicle Powertrains," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 33, no. 9, pp. 7376-7386, 2018.
- [7] K. S. Fuad, H. Hafezi, K. Kauhaniemi, and H. Laaksonen, "Soft Open Point in Distribution Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 210550-210565, 2020.
- [8] Z. Qian, O. Abdel-Rahman, and I. Batarseh, "An Integrated Four-Port DC/DC Converter for Renewable Energy Applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 25, no. 7, pp. 1877-1887, 2010.
- [9] J. M. Bloemink and T. C. Green, "Benefits of Distribution-Level Power Electronics for Supporting Distributed Generation Growth," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 911-919, 2013.
- [10] S. Neira, J. Pereda, and F. Rojas, "Three-Port Full-Bridge Bidirectional Converter for Hybrid DC/DC/AC Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 12, pp. 13077-13084, 2020.
- [11] I. Reditis, M. Dakanalis, E. Koutroulis, and F. D. Kanellos, "Three-Phase Multiport DC-AC Inverter for Interfacing Photovoltaic and Energy Storage Systems to the Electric Grid," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Industrial Electronics*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 982-994, 2023.
- [12] M. Antivachis, N. Kleynhans, and J. W. Kolar, "Three-Phase Sinusoidal Output Buck-Boost GaN Y-Inverter for Advanced Variable Speed AC Drives," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 3459-3476, 2022.
- [13] A. Y. Farag, D. Biadene, P. Mattavelli and T. Younis, "Three-Phase Four-Wire Step-Down Modular Converter for an Enhanced Interlinking in Low-Voltage Hybrid AC/DC Microgrids," *IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 5, pp. 634-647, 2024.